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ANALYSIS OF MARKETING MIX STRATEGIES IN RURAL UMKM (SEBLAK WINWIN CASE STUDY)**Ina ARADA¹, Hendri Hermawan ADINUGRAHA², Ade GUNAWAN³**¹UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan, IndonesiaORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0001-4593-1816>²UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan, IndonesiaORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8394-5776>³UIN K.H. Abdurrahman Wahid Pekalongan, Indonesia<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8479-0641>**Abstract**

This study aims to analyze the marketing mix strategy implemented by Seblak Winwin MSMEs in a rural environment, and identify the main factors that support the success of the business in facing competition in the local culinary industry. Seblak Winwin is one of the culinary MSME players who are able to survive and thrive in the midst of intense competition. This research uses a qualitative approach with a case study method. Data collection techniques were carried out through interviews with managers and consumers as well as direct observation. The data obtained was analyzed inductively to explore the meaning behind the implementation of marketing strategies. The results showed that Seblak Winwin implements a marketing mix strategy that includes four main elements: product, price, place, and promotion. In the product aspect, Seblak Winwin excels through the diversity of toppings and regular updates to maintain consumer interest. Pricing is adjusted to the purchasing power of the surrounding community, especially students, with an affordable price range. The selection of a strategic location by the highway also supports business visibility. In terms of promotion, the word of mouth strategy is the main tool that is considered effective in reaching new consumers. This research contributes to the understanding of local wisdom-based marketing strategies and can be a reference for other culinary MSMEs in increasing competitiveness in a crowded market.

Keywords: Marketing mix, MSMEs, Seblak Winwin, marketing strategy, marketing mix, word of mouth, local culinary, case study.

1. INTRODUCTION

Therefore, this study aims to analyze the marketing strategy implemented by Seblak Winwin and identify the main factors that support its success in facing competition. This study aims to analyze the marketing mix strategy applied by Seblak winwin MSMEs and identify the As a developing country, it is very important for Indonesia to pay attention to MSMEs, because MSMEs have better performance in productive labor, increase high productivity, and are able

to live on the sidelines of large businesses. MSMEs are also agile so that they can survive in unfavorable conditions, such as the current global crisis (Sarfiyah et al., 2019).

Data from BPS and the Ministry of Cooperatives in Wahyudin (2013: 27), of all business classes show that small-scale businesses in Indonesia occupy a portion of around 99%, meaning that almost all businesses in Indonesia are small businesses, only 1% are medium and large businesses (Sarfiyah et al., 2019). This shows that there are many umkm in Indonesia. As a result, there is often competition between one umkm and another. The more sellers there are, the more choices buyers have. Sellers whose prices are higher will certainly be abandoned by buyers.

Marketing mix is a collection of marketing strategies or tools that can be arranged and used by companies to obtain responses as expected from consumers who become their target market (Arif Fakhruddin, Maria Valeria Roelianty, 2022). The culinary industry based on regional specialties is currently popular, including the specialty food from Bandung, namely seblak. Seblak has a distinctive flavor derived from kencur or cukur in Sundanese. The filling of seblak consists of crackers, eggs, dumplings, cilok and meatballs.

Seblak is now one of the favorite foods in various circles. This has led to more and more seblak stalls popping up, creating intense competition among businesses. Including seblak winwin, seblak winwin was established in 2021 with an infrastructure concept where buyers can take as many masks as they like.

Amidst the intense competition of seblak stalls, Seblak Winwin is able to survive and become one of the stalls that is visited by buyers. The success of Seblak Kalisat in attracting consumers compared to its competitors is an interesting phenomenon to study. Understanding the factors that contribute to Seblak Winwin's success can provide greater insight for culinary MSME players in developing their business to remain competitive in an increasingly crowded market.

main factors that support its success in facing competition in the regional food-based culinary industry. To achieve these objectives, this study focuses on several main aspects, namely identifying the marketing mix strategy applied by Seblak winwin MSMEs, analyzing the role of cultural factors and consumption habits of local communities in shaping consumer preferences for seblak products, and assessing the effectiveness of the marketing strategy used in improving the competitiveness of these MSMEs.

This research has significance in filling the gap of previous studies that mostly discuss marketing mix strategies in the field of production. Thus, this research contributes to the field of local wisdom-based marketing strategies in the culinary MSME sector. The benefits of this research are expected to be felt by various parties. For culinary MSMEs, the results of this study can provide insight into effective and locally-based marketing strategies to improve business competitiveness. From the academic side, this research can be an additional reference in the study of MSME marketing strategies with a cultural approach and local consumption habits. Meanwhile, for the government and stakeholders, this research can provide useful information in designing policies that support the development of regional specialty food-based culinary MSMEs. In addition, for consumers, this research can increase their understanding of how cultural factors and consumption habits affect the products they choose and consume.

1.1. Theoretical Review

According to Kotler, marketing mix is a collection of strategies used by companies to consistently achieve their marketing objectives in targeted markets (Ritonga, n.d.). Marketing mix is not a scientific theory, but rather a conceptual framework that assists managers in making key decisions to tailor their products to consumer needs. These tools can be applied to design long-term strategies as well as short-term plans (İşoraité, 2016). According to E. Jerome

McCarthy's view, the main elements that make up the marketing mix are the goods or services offered (product), the cost set for them (price), the way the product is distributed and available to consumers (place), and various efforts to inform and persuade consumers (Gandolfo Dominici, 2009).

According to Neil Borden (1965), it was he who first used the term “marketing mix”. This idea arose from James Culliton's (1948) depiction of a business executive acting like a “concocter” of various components. Borden's initial version of the marketing mix consisted of 12 elements, including product planning, pricing, branding, distribution channels, direct selling, advertising, promotion, packaging, display, service, physical handling, and research and data analysis (Chai Lee Goi, 2009). Later, E. Jerome McCarthy (1964) further developed Borden's concept. McCarthy defined the marketing mix as a combination of all the factors that a marketing manager can manage to meet the needs of a target market. He simplified Borden's 12 elements into four main elements known as the 4Ps, namely product, price, promotion, and place, which are under the control of the marketing manager to satisfy the target market (Chai Lee Goi, 2009).

E. Jerome McCarthy states that there are 4 main elements that make up the marketing mix, including:

1. product

Product is the main component in the marketing mix, so it has a very significant role in the formulation of the overall marketing strategy. Before compiling other marketing mix elements, companies need to first determine the type of product to be developed and marketed.

- Product line refers to a group of products that are closely related, both in terms of function, target market, and distribution channels. Products in a line generally have similar characteristics and are intended to meet the needs of the same consumer segment.
- Product diversification is a strategy to expand the variety of goods or services offered by the company. This diversification can be done through the development of new products or by modifying existing products such as changing the type, color, model, size, or type of product with the main objective of increasing competitiveness and obtaining optimal profits.
- product life cycle (PLC) describes the stages of a product's journey in the market, starting from when it is first introduced, experiencing growth, reaching a point of saturation, until finally experiencing a decline and being withdrawn from circulation. This concept is usually visualized in graphic form and serves as a guide in designing appropriate marketing strategies at each phase of the product cycle.

2. Price

according to Al Baidi (2015), Uzeme and Ohen (2015), and Kotler et al. (2019), is defined as the amount of funds that consumers spend to get a product or service, or as the exchange rate given by consumers to obtain the benefits, ownership, or use of a product. Kotler and Armstrong (2018) identify several indicators in pricing, namely: (a) price affordability, which refers to the financial ability of consumers to buy products at a set price; (b) price compatibility with product quality, where consumers tend to choose higher prices if the quality of the products offered is also superior; and (c) price competitiveness, which considers consumers' decisions to buy a product based on a comparison between the perceived benefits and the costs incurred. In addition, price-benefit compatibility is also an important consideration for consumers, where they compare the price of a product with similar products and consider whether the benefits to be obtained are worth the price to be paid (Ummah, 2019)

3. Place or distribution

Distribution is a series of actions to select and manage marketing channels for products or services through various organizations or individuals that play a role in distributing products or services to target markets. The goal is that consumers can fulfill their needs and desires. In determining the distribution channel, producers need to consider the elements in the distribution mix, which include: the distribution channel system used, the breadth of the distribution range, determining the location of sales, managing product inventory, and the transportation methods used.(Ummah, 2019)

4. Promotion

Promotion is a series of communication and persuasion activities aimed at the market to introduce new products or services. This effort is carried out through various methods, including advertising, face-to-face sales, sales promotion, and publication.

Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) can be defined as economic activities that are generating in nature, owned by individuals or business entities, and have met the requirements as a micro business scale. According to the regulation of law number 20 of 2008 article 1 defines.

1. Micro-enterprises are productive businesses owned by individuals or individual business entities and fulfill specific requirements stipulated in the law.

2. Small Enterprises are independent productive economic businesses, run by individuals or business entities that are not subsidiaries or branches of Medium Enterprises or Large Enterprises, and meet the criteria of small scale in accordance with the law

3. Medium Enterprises are independent productive economic businesses, run by individuals or business entities that are not directly or indirectly affiliated with Small Enterprises or Large Enterprises, and have certain net worth or annual income limits stipulated in the law (Undang-Undang Republik Indonesia Nomor 20 Tahun, 2008).

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2. METHODE

This research method uses a qualitative approach. In qualitative research, the data collection process is not based on existing theories, but on facts found directly in the field. Therefore, data analysis is carried out inductively, starting from empirical findings which are then arranged into hypotheses or theories. Thus, qualitative research aims to build hypotheses through data analysis, while quantitative research aims to test previously established hypotheses(Rahmadi, S.Ag., 2011)

Case study is a type of research conducted in depth on individuals, groups, organizations, programs, or certain activities over a period of time. The aim is to get a comprehensive and in-depth picture of an entity, so that data can be obtained which is then analyzed to formulate a theory. In accordance with procedures in qualitative research, data in case studies are collected through interviews, observations, and documents or archives(Rahmadi, S.Ag., 2011)

The data sources used are primary and secondary. Primary data is the main information obtained directly by researchers during the research process. This data comes from original sources, such as respondents or informants who are directly related to the research variables. The form of primary data can be in the form of observation results, interviews, or filling out questionnaires. In this study, the data source is the manager of the seblak stall and customers(Rukhmana, 2021)

According to Alir (2005) Secondary data is a type of research data obtained through intermediaries or indirect sources. This means that this data is not obtained directly by

researchers, but comes from previously available information, such as documents, literature, or data collected by other parties. Examples of secondary data sources include books, scientific journals, articles, financial reports, and census data collected by government agencies (Rukhmana, 2021).

Data collection techniques using interviews and observations. Interview is a research data collection method carried out through direct conversation or oral question and answer between the researcher (interviewer) and the respondent (interviewee) in order to obtain the information needed in the research. Observation is an activity of observing and recording facts relevant to research needs. Observation is the main foundation in science, because scientists rely on data derived from reality in the field, which is obtained through the observation process (Rahmadi, S.Ag., 2011)

According to Lincoln and Guba (in Maleong, 2016: 189), one important step to ensure the credibility of research results is to use theoretical triangulation techniques. This technique is a way to check data by utilizing elements outside the data itself, namely theory, which is used as a comparison tool or to verify the meaning of the data obtained (Bado, 2021)

3. RESULT

Based on the results of interviews conducted with the manager and four buyers, a number of findings were obtained regarding the implementation of the marketing mix strategy at Seblak Winwin's business. These findings are examined through four aspects, namely product, price, place, and promotion.

a) Product

According to Ainal, the manager of Seblak Winwin, the variety of toppings is one of the main advantages of their products. This aims to prevent consumer saturation with monotonous topping choices. The manager also stated that the variety of toppings is updated regularly, at least once every two to three months. Two out of four buyer respondents stated that the wide variety of toppings made them less bored. Meanwhile, three out of four buyers stated that Winwin's seblak tastes good and has a different flavor compared to seblak from other places, and in accordance with consumer preferences

b) Pricing

Pricing by Seblak Winwin is tailored to market segmentation and business location. The main target market is students and university students, while the business location is in a rural area. The price per serving of seblak varies depending on the toppings chosen, with the range of topping prices ranging from Rp1,000 to Rp5,000. All respondents (four out of four buyers) stated that the prices were affordable and in line with their purchasing power. They also considered the price to be in line with the environment in which the business operates.

c) Place

Seblak Winwin is located on the edge of the highway, which is considered strategic by the manager. This location is considered advantageous, especially during major events such as holidays, as it increases visibility and facilitates the process of direct promotion to new consumers. Most respondents (three out of four buyers) stated that the business location is easily accessible and well known by the surrounding community.

d) Promotion

The manager revealed that currently they rely more on word-of-mouth promotion strategies than through social media, due to limited human resources in digital content management. Nevertheless, the strategy is considered quite effective in reaching new customers. All respondents mentioned that they know Seblak Winwin through recommendations from friends and neighbors.

3.1 Elaborating Marketing Mix Practices Based on Interview Results

- Product

According to Kotler, Keller, Brady, Goodman, Hansen (2019), a product is anything that can be offered to the market to satisfy consumer wants and needs (Ummah, 2019). Product Diversification is an expansion of the selection of goods and services sold by the company, by adding new products or improving the type, color, fashion, size, type of existing products in order to obtain maximum profit. (2) this is in line with what seblak winwin does by changing product displays once every 2-3 days.

- Place

The faster the product reaches the point of sale, the more likely it is to satisfy customers and increase brand loyalty, therefore, the place factor is very important in ensuring the competitiveness of your product in the market (Agustinah, 2021). Therefore, the manager chooses a place on the highway so that the product can be recognized more widely.

- Promotion

Word of mouth information is one of the effective promotional strategies, because those who will inform it are users or consumers voluntarily without realizing it because of satisfaction with the services or products provided. This promotion is the main means for managers to promote seblak winwin. According to Ali (2010) Word of mouth is the most powerful medium in communicating goods or services to two or more consumers (Haque-fawzi et al., 2022). Buyers will voluntarily promote seblak winwin to their relatives, friends and neighbors as evidenced by all respondents getting info from friends' recommendations and they will also voluntarily recommend seblak winwin.

- Price

Value Based Pricing is the pricing of prices seen from products perceived by customers, both economic, functional, and psychological benefits (Silalahi & Andari, 2016). Seblak Winwin targets students in rural areas. They set an affordable price of Rp1,000-Rp5,000 per topping, as they understand the purchasing power of their consumers when viewed from the local economy. All buyers stated that the price of seblak is affordable and in line with the quality.

4. CONCLUSION

This study shows that the marketing mix strategy implemented by Seblak Winwin MSMEs reflects a good understanding of the needs and characteristics of local consumers. In terms of products, the variety of toppings offered regularly is an added value that prevents consumer saturation and creates its own uniqueness. In terms of pricing, the determination that is tailored to the purchasing power of the community, especially students and university students, shows the effective implementation of the value-based pricing strategy. The strategic location of the business on the edge of the highway provides advantages in terms of accessibility and visibility, thus strengthening the position of the business in the midst of competition. Although promotion

is still limited to word-of-mouth, this approach has proven to be quite effective in reaching new consumers, especially through recommendations from satisfied customers. In addition, the public's preference for specialty foods such as seblak shows that cultural factors and local consumption habits play an important role in shaping the marketing strategy implemented.

5. REFERENCES

- Agustinah, F. (2021). Konsep 4P dan 7P. In *Manajemen Pemasaran (Perspektif Digital Marketing)*.
- Arif Fakhrudin, Maria Valeria Roelianty, A. (2022). Bauran Pemasaran. *Andrew's Disease of the Skin Clinical Dermatology.*, 7–16.
- Bado, B. (2021). Model Pendekatan Kualitatif: Telaah Dalam Metode Penelitian Ilmiah. In *Pengantar Metode Kualitatif*.
- Chai Lee Goi. (2009). A review of marketing mix: 4Ps or more? *International Journal of Marketing Studies*, 1(1), 2–16. <https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/006a/f4780f1cff9f7075ab5b7073f4cebb32c3d5.pdf>
- Gandolfo Dominici. (2009). From Marketing Mix to E-Marketing Mix: A Literature Overview and Classification by Gandolfo Dominici :: SSRN. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 4(9), 17–24. https://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=1961974
- Haque-fawzi, M. G., Iskandar, ahmad syarief, Erlangga, H., Nurjaya, Sumarsi, D., & I. (2022). STRATEGI PEMASARAN Konsep, Teori dan Implementasi. In *Pascal Books*. <http://repository.ibs.ac.id/id/eprint/4973>
- Işoraitè, M. (2016). Marketing Mix Theoretical Aspects. *International Journal of Research - GRANTHAALAYAH*, 4(6), 25–37. <https://doi.org/10.29121/granthaalayah.v4.i6.2016.2633>
- Rahmadi, S.Ag., M. P. . (2011). Pengantar Metodologi Penelitian. In *Journal of Physics A: Mathematical and Theoretical* (Vol. 44, Issue 8). [https://idr.uin-antasari.ac.id/10670/1/PENGANTAR METODOLOGI PENELITIAN.pdf](https://idr.uin-antasari.ac.id/10670/1/PENGANTAR%20METODOLOGI%20PENELITIAN.pdf)
- Ritonga, W. (n.d.). *2022-06-02-Buku-Manajemen-Pemasaran-1* (p. 98).
- Rukhmana, T. (2021). Jurnal Edu Research Indonesian Institute For Corporate Learning And Studies (IICLS) Page 25. *Jurnal Edu Research : Indonesian Institute For Corporate Learning And Studies (IICLS)*, 2(2), 28–33.
- Silalahi, A., & Andari, R. (2016). Pengaruh Value Based Pricing Terhadap Keputusan Berkunjung Di Taman Rekreasi Kota Bunga Cianjur (Survei terhadap Wisatawan Nusantara Taman Rekreasi Kota Bunga Cianjur). *THE Journal : Tourism and Hospitality Essentials Journal*, 1(2), 67. <https://doi.org/10.17509/thej.v1i2.1882>
- Ummah, M. S. (2019). No 主観的健康感を中心とした在宅高齢者における健康関連指標に関する共分散構造分析Title. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 11(1), 1–14. http://scioteca.caf.com/bitstream/handle/123456789/1091/RED2017-Eng-8ene.pdf?sequence=12&isAllowed=y%0Ahttp://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.regsciurbeco.2008.06.005%0Ahttps://www.researchgate.net/publication/305320484_SISTEM_PEMBETUNGAN_TERPUSAT_STRATEGI_MELESTARI
- Undang-Undang Republik Indonesia Nomor 20 Tahun. (2008). *Undang-Undang Republik Indonesia Nomor 20 Tahun 2008. 1.*